

ERGA Pilot Project Data Sharing Policy

Version 1

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As a public service, and in accordance to the three pillars of the United Nations Convention of Biological Diversity and its Nagoya Protocol; the conservation, sustainable use, and fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from biodiversity resources, the European Reference Genome Atlas (ERGA) Pilot Project is making both the raw data (ONT, PacBio HiFi, IsoSeq, HiC, PCR Free Illumina and RNASeq reads) and the corresponding genome assemblies and annotations for all species available to the ERGA community prior to scientific publication. To balance the importance to ERGA that all Pilot Project data be made openly available and accessible as soon as possible, while safeguarding the interests of our contributing ERGA Genome Teams, we are reserving a maximum of two years after data generation for ERGA scientists to publish on the genome sequencing and analysis without concerns about preemption by other groups. The data will be made available on an ERGA cloud storage facility, and access to the cloud storage will require acceptance of this policy. Project teams may opt to make their data openly accessible and reusable in advance of formal publication. This option will be noted in the cloud storage metadata.

We strongly encourage researchers to contact us at pilot@erga-biodiversity.eu if there are any queries about referencing or publishing analysis based on pre-publication data obtained via our ERGA Nextcloud instance. **By accessing these data, you agree not to publish any articles containing analyses of genes or genomic data on a whole genome or chromosome scale prior to: 1) having obtained consent to do so; 2) publication, by the Genome Team's associated PI found in genome_teams.txt and/or collaborators of a comprehensive genome analysis.** Analyses include the use of the data in developing and improving genomics

procedures, identification of complete (whole genome) sets of general, coding and noncoding genomic features, whole-genome- or chromosome-scale comparisons with other species and use of the assembly as a platform for population genomics analyses.

The embargo on publication of analyses by researchers outside of the corresponding Pilot Project Genome Team will extend until the publication of the sequencing project is accepted, but no longer than two years. After this, all publications or presentations using prepublication data accessed through the cloud repository should clearly acknowledge the contributing genome team and the ERGA Consortium for facilitating the genomic resources allowing this particular research to be carried out.

ERGA Pilot data in the cloud repository may be freely downloaded and used by all within ERGA who respect the restrictions in the previous paragraphs. The assembly and sequence data should not be redistributed or repackaged without permission from the Genome Team's associated PI. Exemptions previously mentioned relating to raw data and genome assembly and annotation pre-publication release must be agreed upon by the ERGA Pilot Executive Committee, are subject to all ERGA associated sequencing centre's rules and regulations and the terms agreed upon in the Material Transfer Agreement.